

Co-creating rural digital policy across borders: A Living Lab-based double diamond approach

Authors

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Abstract

This research-in-progress applies the Double Diamond design model and Living Lab (LL) methodology to co-create rural digital policy in the cross-border regions of Muodoslompolo (Sweden) and Muonio (Finland). Drawing on participatory speculative and critical design methods, such as cultural probes, design fiction, and scenario-based workshops, the project engages diverse stakeholders through the PentaHelix model. Early activities, including interdisciplinary workshops, interviews, and community engagement, have informed a draft policy prototype and a prioritization matrix aligned with key Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The study contributes both practically, by developing a context-sensitive digital policy and action plan, and academically, by advancing LL practices in rural, cross-border settings. The proposed approach offers a replicable model for inclusive and participatory policymaking in underrepresented regions.

Key words

Living Lab, Rural, Digital, Policy, PentaHelix, Double Diamond

Introduction

Rural areas are often marginalized in digital transformation efforts due to a combination of structural, infrastructural, and socio-political limitations (Habibipour et al., 2021; Lindberg, 2024; Lindberg, J. et al., 2021). These issues become even more complex in cross-border regions, where divergent governance systems and digital service ecosystems coexist. The Muodoslompolo region in Sweden and the Muonio region in Finland exemplify this situation, with communities that share challenges and opportunities but operate under different national frameworks. In response to these shared needs, this research-in-progress outlines a participatory and design-oriented process for the development of a science-based digital policy that is rooted in the lived experiences of rural residents.

The project integrates the structured design process of the Double Diamond model (Kochanowska et al., 2022) with the participatory methodology of Living Labs (LLs), utilizing insights from participatory speculative and critical design methodologies (e.g., Vardzell et al. 2013, Dunne & Raby 2013, Iivari et al. 2022, Ventä-Olkkonen et al. 2021) with specifically tailored for rural contexts. The paper is guided by the following research questions:

RQ1: How can a participatory, speculative, critical Living Lab (LL) process be applied in digital policy development for rural areas?

RQ2: How might the scale of the rural context (e.g., population size, geographic area) affect the LL process for digital policy development?

The Double Diamond model offers a clear progression from problem exploration to solution delivery, while the LL principles guide the participatory, speculative, critical processes that underpin the research. Together, they form the foundation of a cross-border digital policy development process that is both systematic and responsive to local needs.

Previous Research

Urban Living Labs (ULLs) is a promising but underdeveloped tool for addressing challenges in deprived urban contexts. This article focuses on a shift moving from technologically driven Living Labs to socially oriented ULLs that prioritize empowerment and local capacity-building (Cognetti and Maranghi, 2023). Empowerment, inclusivity, and local leadership are central elements in the rural Living Lab approach used to enhance digital services and strengthen rural retail, aiming to improve the quality of life in villages (Lindberg, 2024).

ULLs have the potential to influence policy by making local, often overlooked, competencies visible. This shift helps transform how residents are perceived—from being passive “targets” of interventions to active “agents” in policymaking (Cognetti & Maranghi, 2023). A similar dynamic is evident in rural development, where women often engage through unofficial networks beyond formal organisations, challenging and reshaping traditional boundaries between public and private roles (Arora-Jonsson, 2017). This form of grassroots participation is often described as self-organisation, where citizens take the initiative to drive change in their communities (Edelenbos & van Meerkerk, 2016). In rural Living Labs in a north Sweden setting, the implementation of digital services has further supported this by opening new spaces for participation and promoting a relational view of competence (Lindberg, 2024). By engaging in small-scale, robust LLs, like in the

SoHoLab and Digiby projects, LLs have provided evidence-based micro-interventions that can feed into broader policy agendas (Cognetti & Maranghi, 2023; Lindberg, 2024; Lindberg et al. 2025).

From a policymaker's perspective, it is important to create opportunities for direct interaction with residents. One effective method is to establish local “pop-up venues” in villages, which can help reach individuals outside established networks (Lindberg et al., 2024). These interactions should follow a LL approach, prioritizing listening and co-exploration over predefined solutions. The goal is to act as a facilitator—supporting residents and organisations in voicing their perspectives and contributing meaningfully to policy development (Lindberg, 2024).

This study aims to contribute to the LL literature by emphasizing the importance of acknowledging intra-rural diversity when designing participatory digital policy processes. While ULLs have been reframed as tools for empowerment and decentralized governance, RLLs introduce specific conditions related to distance, limited resources, and tight-knit social structures. By focusing on the interaction between rural centers and villages in a cross-border context, the study demonstrates how RLLs can support place-based innovation, strengthen local capacity, and tailor digital policy to the realities of rural life.

Conceptual Framework

The Double Diamond model, developed by the UK Design Council, provides a four-phase structure that is widely used in design and innovation. These phases are called Discover, Define, Develop, and Deliver which facilitate both divergent and convergent thinking (Kochanowska et al., 2022). See Figure 1. In this project, the model serves as the

overarching structure for designing and implementing a digital policy that emerges from community-identified needs and is refined through collaborative prototyping and feedback. To support this design structure to a higher level, the project applies the LL approach as conceptualized in recent research on rural innovation ecosystems (Bergvall-Kareborn et al., 2009; Habibipour et al., 2021). The research project integrates seven foundational elements to operationalize the LL approach: early and continuous stakeholder engagement, value co-creation, openness and transparency, iterative processes, real-life experimentation, distributed decision-making, and social inclusivity. To ensure broad and balanced participation throughout all phases of the policy development process, the research project employs the Penta-Helix model, which engages stakeholders from academia, government, industry, civil society, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs).

We will augment the RLL approach by integrating insights from participatory speculative and critical design traditions (see e.g., Bardzell et al. 2013, Dunne & Raby 2013, livari et al. 2024a, livari et al. 2024b, Sharma et al. 2023, Ventä-Olkkonen et al. 2021). Speculative and critical design, developed within Design Research tradition, are specific in their approach towards design as critique and in their strong futures orientation. Such design approaches wish to criticize and question the status quo, to introduce alternative values to mainstream design, to provoke, to explore ethical issues, or to raise awareness and debate (e.g., Bardzell et al. 2013, Dunne & Raby 2013). Critical design may be geared at exploring the current problematic conditions made visible through design, or it may be a highly activist endeavour working towards social or political change (livari et al. 2022). Speculative design is heavily geared at raising speculation, exploration, and debate on (desirable, probable, plausible, possible, impossible, digital) futures, which can be used to stimulate action to shape the future but also it may also act as a valuable critique and commentary of the present (Dunne & Raby 2013).

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Figure 1. The Double Diamond design thinking process (Adopted from the Design Council).

In the RLL approach explored in this project, we have the following commitments. We see the local participants possessing invaluable expertise of their local conditions that should be utilized in the design of digital policies affecting their lives. We see their participation as their right and a necessary condition for high quality outcomes. We see digital policy making as a complex power-laden endeavour requiring multiple types of expertise, which is not possessed by one party only, but negotiation, translation and co-creation among various participants and types of expertise is needed (Väyrynen et al. 2025). By relying on participatory speculative and critical design, we work towards empowerment of local participants in policy processes by inviting them into 1) critical exploration and reflection of the current realities, 2) collective dreaming of desirable (digital) futures, and 3) collective action taking towards that direction (see e.g., livari et al. 2024a, livari et al. 2024b).

Context

The surrounding region of Muonio and Muodoslompolo present a distinctive interplay of natural landscapes, cultural heritage, and cross-border cooperation. Muodoslompolo is a small village situated approximately 110 kilometres north of the central town of Pajala, with a population of around 70 residents. The village hosts a privately owned grocery store, while the local school, although closed in the early 2000s, still remains a physical landmark. On the Finnish side of the border, the municipality of Muonio has approximately 2,430 inhabitants and offers well-developed community services, including schools, shops, and hotels. Muonio's economy is largely oriented towards tourism, with popular activities such as dog sledding, snowmobiling, reindeer safaris, and winter fishing. The Olos mountain area is particularly notable for its extensive ski and snowmobile infrastructure. Concession-based reindeer herding constitutes a vital aspect of both the

cultural identity and economic activity of the region. The area lies between two core reindeer herding zones and is intersected by traditional migration routes used by reindeer.

The local landscape is characterised by a diverse mix of developed land and natural forests. Architectural traditions in the Tornedalen region include enclosed farmyards dating from the 1920s to the 1940s, reflecting a historically significant rural built environment. The region's waterways are important sites for swimming, fishing, and outdoor recreation. While the number of holiday homes around the lakes is relatively limited, public access to the beaches is largely preserved. The lakes in this region form part of the Torne River catchment area, designated as a Natura 2000 site due to its high ecological and good chemical status.

Research Methodology

This research adopts a participatory, exploratory approach grounded in the Double Diamond design model (Kochanowska et al., 2022) and guided by key principles from the LL methodology (Habibipour et al., 2021; Ståhlbröst, 2012) and participatory speculative and critical design (e.g., Bardzell et al. 2013, Dunne & Raby 2013, Ventä-Olkkonen et al. 2021). The aim is to support the development of a cross-border digital policy tailored to the rural realities of the Muodoslompolo (Sweden) and Muonio (Finland) region. The Double Diamond model, with its four phases, namely Discover, Define, Develop, and Deliver, offers a structured yet flexible process. The LL principles bring focus to collaboration, real-life context, iteration, and inclusiveness. Various design methods such as cultural probes, personas and scenarios, miracle discussions, design fiction workshops, and drama and activism-based methods will be explored with participants to probe their current realities as well as to explore their visions for the future (see e.g., livari et al. 2024a, livari et al. 2024b, livari et al. 2023, Sebastian et al. 2024, Sharma et al. 2022, Ventä-Olkkonen et al. 2021, Ventä-Olkkonen et al. 2025).

As a first step, an interdisciplinary workshop was held with four researchers from Luleå University of Technology and six from the University of Oulu. The purpose was to shape the structure of the policy co-creation process. The workshop outlined preliminary ideas on which stakeholders might be involved, what methods could be relevant in each Double Diamond phase, and how to link these to concrete, manageable actions. Discussions focused on identifying opportunities for stakeholder engagement, mapping challenges in the rural policy context, and exploring how LL principles could be meaningfully applied within a limited and localized project. The emphasis was on staying grounded in the realities of a small-scale initiative, where flexibility, responsiveness, and simplicity are key.

The workshop lasted four hours and included a preliminary evaluation of the project's alignment with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

To start with the empirical data collection, a short field visit to Muodoslompolo was conducted, including one interview and a small focus group with local residents and members of the village association. While limited in scale, the discussions pointed to key cross-border concerns: dental and healthcare, elderly care, schools and education, environmental issues (particularly water) art and culture, and business collaboration. These initial insights will help shape the priorities and methods of the upcoming stakeholder workshops.

Preliminary Insights and Expected Outcomes

Although the project is ongoing, early insights have emerged through the Double Diamond process. The Discover phase involved participatory mapping with PentaHelix actors in Sweden and Finland, using methods such as interviews, focus groups, and speculative design to identify local challenges in healthcare, education, environment, culture, and entrepreneurship. These findings informed alignment with SDGs 4, 8, 10, 11, and 17. In the Define phase, community insights were used to draft a digital policy framework and develop a prioritization matrix connecting key policy areas to SDGs, particularly SDGs 13, 14, and 15.

Moving into the Develop phase, the focus will be on evaluating a co-created policy prototype through community-based activities using personas, dramatized scenarios, and visual storytelling. These methods aim to validate the relevance and comprehensibility of the proposed policy with rural stakeholders.

Finally, the Deliver phase is expected to culminate in a finalized cross-border digital policy and action plan, co-published through a hybrid community event. This deliverable will include an annex mapping policy action to SDG targets and document the participatory process outputs. Additionally, recordings and outcomes from the community engagement activities will serve as both dissemination material and evidence of process legitimacy.

Discussion and Contributions

This research in progress paper contributes to the evolving LL literature by demonstrating how LL principles can be effectively adapted to support digital policy development in small-scale, cross-border rural contexts. While many LL implementations focus on urban innovation or technology prototyping, this initiative applies LL thinking to participatory

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policymaking, addressing challenges of limited resources, dispersed populations, and complex multi-level governance. Early participatory activities, including interdisciplinary researcher workshops, site visits, interviews, and a focus group, have underscored the importance of aligning methods with local rhythms, relationships, and lived realities. This approach responds to recent calls to shift LLs toward socially responsive and empowerment-oriented practices (Cognetti & Maranghi, 2023; Lindberg, 2024).

Insights from the Double Diamond-based workshop revealed strong interest in tangible, localized actions such as collaboration with schools and cultural institutions, visualizing business cooperation, and involving students in co-creation. These activities supported early mapping of key stakeholders and policy needs, with sustainability goals (SDGs 13, 14, and 15) providing an important framing lens.

The project is currently situated in the Discover phase. As it progresses through the Define, Develop, and Deliver stages, the Double Diamond model offers structural guidance, while the LL methodology ensures iterative, inclusive, and grounded engagement. Ultimately, the project aims to generate both practical tools for rural digital policy and theoretical insights for extending LL research into underrepresented rural settings.

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